

INCREASING NEEDS IS AN IMPORTANT FACTOR OF SOCIETY'S DEVELOPMENT

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Human society is made up of people. Man is the highest of all creatures. He is distinguished from other creatures by his intellectual perception, understanding of reality, and conscious activity. He has to satisfy his various needs in order to survive, because he cannot live without them. In order to live, he must have food, clothing, shelter, and security. He does not take the products he needs ready-made from nature, but produces them himself. Creativity is another important feature that distinguishes it from the animal world, as well as intelligence and language. As long as a person lives, he has needs. Needs have an objective (material and spiritual) nature, but they are perceived and manifested subjectively (satisfied by a person). The whole life, activities and actions of a person are aimed at satisfying these needs.

First of all, the human body constantly needs internal and external information received by the senses for its normal functioning. As a result, a person feels natural physiological feelings such as hunger, thirst, sleep, cold or heat, is motivated to learn, watch movies, sing or listen, communicate with people, make new inventions, create new products. A certain unit of society: parents, relatives, friends, neighbors, acquaintances, people who have met by chance, kindergarten, school, educational system, etc., appear as a source of external information of a person.

All human habits, emotions, knowledge and life experience, evaluation of one or another thing, preconceived or involuntary desires are formed on the basis of information received by the body. Newly received information creates new needs, clarifies the existing ones, sometimes reduces or eliminates them, and sometimes enriches them.

The demand for all material and non-material, spiritual blessings necessary for people's living and all-round development constitutes their vital needs. As a conscious being, man uses his mind to satisfy his needs. The need to satisfy needs pushes him to practical creativity and various activities. Human needs are diverse. While he lives, he participates in physiological processes, satisfies his material and economic interests, demands, acquires knowledge, communicates with others, makes friends, etc. Needs differ from each other in different forms, characteristics, quality, character, quantity and other aspects.

Each person has his own measure of value, and what is valued and vital to one person may not be of any importance to another. Of course, there are biophysiological and primary social needs that are considered necessary for human existence. But he also has secondary complex needs (many spiritual needs), the failure of which can lead to decline (crisis) of human life and rise of ignorance. Each person determines what needs are most necessary for him. In addition to individual needs, there are family, collective, professional, caste, class, and national needs. They are, of course, common to the relevant unit of society, regardless of the degree to which its particular members realize it. For example, some of its members (husband, wife or one of the children) may not understand the family needs arising from the interests of the family, and may put their selfish desires above them. But this does not mean that the family does not have common needs. The needs of the family are not measured against the needs of the husband or wife. For example: the needs of the family are met, not the needs of the husband, by buying a housekeeper by buying household goods, and buying a car.

The issue of needs and their essence is one of the historically priority topics of social thought and social consciousness.

Since ancient times, man, his social essence, and his role in the development of society have been one of the important areas of the system of philosophical sciences (philosophy, psychology, sociology, economics, foundations of spirituality, ethics, aesthetics, etc.).

Philosophical and social science disciplines have given different definitions to the concept of needs. In particular, "Philosophy" (in the dictionary): "Need is a natural characteristic that appears on the basis of human requirements; it is noted that a living creature is dependent on the obvious conditions for its existence. It is emphasized that human activity is different in terms of form and essence compared to other beings. If in creatures (animals) the needs are in accordance with the natural purpose (animals do not carry out creative activities due to the absence of consciousness), the source of human activity is material and spiritual needs. Since a person acquires both individuality and sociality at the same time, his needs have a personal and social nature.

Also "Philosophy. We see that the definition given to the concept of need in "Encyclopedic dictionary" differs from the one above: "Need is the need for things necessary for living and functioning. The need is not only for the human organism, but also for plants, enterprises, political parties, public organizations and any other natural and social systems". The following points follow from this

definition: need is not only a human reality, but also refers to the whole being (animals, plants). However, needs are understood and satisfied only by a person who is a conscious being. We can know the difference between the needs of the animal world and the needs of humans through the explanation given in the explanatory dictionary of psychology.

In the explanatory dictionary of psychology, needs are defined as: "Need is an activity motive reflecting the necessary conditions that ensure the life of the organism; feeling an unmet need; The need is common to both humans and animals. However, animal and human needs are fundamentally different from each other: animal needs have only natural, organic qualities, and human needs are subject to social laws, new socio-historical requirements" - is defined as.

In the system of economic sciences, needs are mentioned together with production and natural resources. The satisfaction of material and spiritual needs of a person requires material production, more precisely, natural resources. As human needs are satisfied, the natural resources available in nature will decrease proportionally. Creating a product that satisfies a human need creates the need to create new products. For example: a new car meets the needs of the family, fuel and spare parts are necessary for the movement of the car.

In the economy, market laws are also directly related to human needs. Production of products depends on demand, and demand depends on need. The greater the needs of people, the greater the demand, the higher the production and creativity.

Needs are the demand and need for things necessary to maintain the life activity of the organism, human personality, social group, society as a whole. One of the fundamental categories of theoretical and practical economics. The need expresses the connections between the subject and its activities and is manifested in goals, inclinations, aspirations and, ultimately, in behavior and character. Work, knowledge, communication depending on the field of activity; material, spiritual depending on the object; depending on the subject, it can be individual (personal), group, collective, social need. The general law of needs is their direct dependence on human activity in general, and social production in particular. At the same time, the need, which is the motivating force for activity, has a selective effect on life conditions, determines their specific aspects, stimulates one or another activity method and the production of objects that satisfy the need. For example, people's need for a car at one time led to the

beginning of the search for their creation, which led to the emergence of a whole industry.

In short, the needs defined by economic, political, and social development needs, combined with spirituality, are the main force that accelerates the development of society. Where there is no need, there is no progress and no growth.

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